

Feministic Perspective of Shashi Deshpande in a Matter of Time

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Abstract

The present paper entitled FEMINISTIC PERSPECTIVE OF SHASHI DESHPANDE IN A MATTER OF TIME speaks about feministic views of the novelist. Her chief concern is to expose the sufferings of women in the hands of their members of the family, including their husbands. This novel also depicts the picture of a lady, namely, Sumi, who is not exploited by her husband directly, but she suffers due to sudden and selfish abscond of her husband, Gopal, leaving all responsibilities of the family upon her shoulders. This novel portrays the pathetic condition of Sumi and other women characters in a patriarchal set-up. Shashi Deshpande gives a sensitive portrayal of female protagonists attempt to be liberal and independent in thinking, making decisions, taking actions, working, and creating on the same terms as men. They try to move towards self-realization, self-investigation, and self-assertion. They fight against age-old man-made rules with the help of their inner strength. Her novel A Matter of Time explores the many facts of feminine sufferings in India, like gender differences and passive experiences, familial relationships. Sumi in A Matter of Time is an emancipated lady who undertakes her journey to liberation after she is deserted by her husband Gopal after twenty-three years of married life. The novel puts forth Shashi Deshpande's views on women's liberation.

Keywords: feminist, aspiration, submissive, marriage, family empowerment, patriarchy.

Shashi Deshpande's novels are always dealt with woman, her anguish and deprivation, tensions and irritations, grief and sorrow. Unable to disobey social conventions or traditional morality, the middle-class women themselves are entangled by desires and despairs, fears and hopes loves and hates, withdrawal and alienation, suppression and oppression, marital discord and male chauvinism. Indeed, Shashi Deshpande's central theme is a woman's struggle, in the context of contemporary Indian society, her effort to find and maintain her identity as a wife.

Her writings are a sincere effort to examine the hidden psyche and consciousness of women caught in the trap of patriarchal society. She has a thorough understanding of the fundamental reality of the tragic life of women, victimized creatures. She deplores that they have always been socially, emotionally, psychologically, sexually, and biologically suppressed and exploited in a male-dominated society.

This novel describes the picture of a lady, namely Sumi, suffers due to sudden and selfish escape of Gopal, her husband leaving all

responsibilities of the family upon her shoulders. One evening Sumi's world is collapsed as her husband Gopal walks out from home, leaving her with three daughters Aru, Charu and Seema. The pain of the breakdown of the family upsets Aru who considers herself responsible for her father's death and sets out to undo it. Sumi along with her daughters go back to their ancestral house where her mother Kalyani had been living in a depressive and strange silence, striving to make sense of her relation with her husband who hasn't talked to her for years. Sumi finds comfort in taking up her dream career; Aru understands her mother's indifference and her father's desertion.

The novel revolves around an urban middle-class family consisting of Gopal and Sumi and their three daughters. Sumi maintains long silence in her adverse circumstances without complaining against anyone and accepts it in a mute way. Gopal has a cordial relationship with his wife and daughters so long as he lives with them, but he deserts them suddenly for a reason not known to others. Among the daughters, Aru is the eldest one who proves herself more intelligent, wise, and respectful towards her whole family, including her grand-father and grand-mother. Sumi, an educated lady, matured enough to know the reality of life and truth of the world. She is ready to face any hard situation in her life, so she does not stop Gopal leaving the family.

A Matter of Time is a story of female emancipation as it describes the journey of Sumi to her liberation. She has much concern about her career. So that she does not see herself lonely for her grief. With full of courage and boldness, she astonishes everyone. She works hard because she wishes to pay her daughters fee and their other demands not expecting from anybody.

Deshpande wants her women not to remain passive and submissive but to emerge as a firm, self-assured and ambitious characters in their ways, attempting to and succeeding in striking a delicate balance between traditional beliefs and individual needs. She portrays her married women not to be mere shadows of their husbands. They refuse to accept them as sheltering trees. They never follow their husbands blindly and mechanically. She makes them realize that true liberty lies in having the courage to do what one accepts is the right thing to do and the resolution to stick to it. She makes them be new and modern in the true sense of the term.

In A Matter of Time, education is the only way through which the women's knowledge can be expanded, and her place can be assured in the society to which she belongs. She regards women individuals equal to men, as competent to them with a lot of abilities and potentials. Her female protagonists undergo a psychological journey of self-realization to trace themselves as free and independent individuals. They can discover and assert their self-identity and self-realization. They have an appetite to make themselves bold and confident, to detect space for themselves to grow and develop on their own. Though, many of her female characters are emotionally and sexually frustrated; they struggle against conventions and traditions within the framework of a family.

Gopal lodges a few miles away from his wife and daughters in the house of Shankar, one of his old students. Gopal's desertion disturbs the very peace, happiness, and balance of the family. Sumi's return to the Big House after Gopal's abandonment is a matter of shame both for Aru, her eldest daughter, and Kalyani, her mother. Kalyani, Devaki, Premi, and others feel sorry for the failure of her marital life. The family renders to take her into confidence and even to comfort her. Sumi never wishes to unlock her heart to anybody.

After Gopal's desertion, though, Sumi seems to be calm and undisturbed, her grief, fury, and humiliation are so deep and severe that she becomes anxious and restless. Her silence turns into a cry of despair. She feels alone and emotionally disturbed. She comforts herself when she says: "It takes time to get used to sharing your life with another person, now I have to get used to being alone" (23).

She determines to adjust herself with changing circumstances and to accept her tragic life. She is bothered about her daughters. She asks herself: "Am I the enemy? Do my daughters blame me for

what Gopal has done? Do they think it is my fault? Why can't I talk to them, tell them what I feel, how it was? Why can't I open my heart to them?" (23).

Aru proves herself strong and bold in adverse circumstances. She gives her full support to her mother at her level best. She behaves to be a responsible member of the family. Sumi does not wish to be a parasite in the family. She, therefore, seeks a temporary job of a teacher to support herself and her daughters. It is hard to Sumi to handle her daughters. On the surface, they appear to live a normal course of their lives, but Sumi notices some change in them. They have withdrawn into themselves. Aru's reserve has changed into secretiveness. Charu turns into a single-minded book worm. She appears to be interested in her college, with her evening classes and books. Seema keeps distance both from her mother and her sisters. Uneasily, she thinks: "I don't want my daughters to live with a hand clasped over their mouths like Premi and I had to" (59).

She does not like her daughters to be silent sufferers. Sumi has no hatred for her husband. Aru is not ready to forget and forgive her father's action. She wishes even her mother not to forget it. She asks her mother to consult the lawyer and to do something against him. Sumi does not go with her. She just laughs and says:

Gopal has outsmarted the law. He's given us all that he had. And he has nothing now, not even a proper job... So what can the law make him do? ... Do you want to punish him, Aru? I don't. I'm not interested. I just want to get on with my life... Let him go, Aru, just let him go. This is not good for you(61).

Gopal's abandonment creates a vacuum in Sumi's life. She traces out the clues in the past acts and utterances of Gopal. During her search for the house, she happens to meet her husband for the first time since the day he left home. They cannot speak freely, and they feel the burden of unsaid things. They become speechless when they look at each other. She realizes:

We can never be together again. All these days I have thought of him as if he has been suspended in space, in nothingness, since he left us. But he has gone on living; his life has moved on, it will go on without me. So has mine. Our lives have diverged; they now move separately, two different streams. (85)

Sumi proves herself to be a woman of daring, self-possessed, dignity, self-sufficiency and self-fulfillment by taking care of her daughters without the help of her husband. She manages her family in her adversity. Though she has full of grief and humiliation, she makes herself calm and controlled.

Gopal's departure makes the whole family into collapse. This unexpected crisis in her life gives her a chance to prove her inner strength and potentiality. She patiently accepts the role of a deserted wife. She does not encourage any discussion over it and prefers to be silent. Her self-respecting nature and self-trust do not allow her to accept any monetary help from her close relatives. She is ready to face the challenges of her life. She never expects pity or concern from her family members. Sumi's decision to learn to ride the scooter indicates that she is confident enough to live her life all by herself.

A Matter of Time is not about only Sumi or Gopal; it portrays the life of four generations of women. Manorama belongs to the first generation is dead, but her presence is always felt, Kalyani is of the second generation, Sumi is of the third generation, and Aru is of the fourth generation. Manorama was the daughter of a poor man and was married in a very wealthy family. Kalyani, Sumi, and Aru are the direct victims of patriarchal society. Sumi, after Gopal's desertion, gets a new identity. She changes herself into an independent woman. Aru, the fourth generation, is constantly trying hard to come to terms with reality.

She has to overcome this shock and establish her life in society. Sumi bears everything with silence. She does not ask the reasons for her husband's desertion. Sumi longs to be independent.

She transforms her emptiness into meaningful to redefine her identity. She began a new phase of her life and dedicated herself to her job and her children. In Indian society, A woman has a happy life when she has got the dependent marital life. But Sumi revolts against this tradition. She starts writing and her first play, *The Gardener's Son*, becomes successful.

Sumi gets a job and decides to go to Devgiri. Aru is shocked when she knows about it, but Sumi says, "Be happy for me, Aru. This is the first thing in my life. I think that I've got for myself" (220). Only when Sumi attains economic freedom and immerses herself in creative writing, she becomes more dynamic. Sumi meets with an accident while riding a scooter with her father, Shripati. Both Sumi's and Shripati's bodies are found heavily injured. Sumi dies just before she is going to start a new life. But she has proved her identity and found a meaningful existence before her death.

Traditionally, marriage is the "only means of support and the sole justification" of a woman's existence. But Deshpande has revealed that a woman can also find meaningful existence even outside marriage. Sumi's daughters also establish their identity. Aru is going to be a lawyer, and Charu is on her way to becoming a doctor. They are loved by two capable young men -Rohit and Hrishikesh. When Sumi is ready for a fuller life, it is an irony of fate that her life cut off in the prime. It is a pity that Sumi dies when she gets a job to support herself and her daughters. She would have become an economically independent woman with a modern and matured outlook towards life; and at the same time, a loving and responsible mother.

The novel illustrates how women are being treated in India. Though Deshpande brings out the submissiveness of her women characters, she enables them to move in a positive direction to maximize their potential.

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